

Psychological Empowerment in Relation to Public Elementary Teachers Work Performance in Davao Oriental

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Abstract. The study aimed to determine the influence of psychological empowerment on teachers' work performance. The researcher used a non-experimental quantitative research method to establish their association with the 158 elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District in Davao Oriental as the study's respondents. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized to select the respondents. Additionally, a Non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and Multiple Regression Analysis were the statistical tools used in the study to interpret the data collected. The findings revealed that the extent of psychological empowerment of teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental, in terms of meaning, competence, autonomy, and Influence, was described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested. The extent of elementary teachers' work performance in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental, in terms of task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior, was extensive. Meanwhile, correlation analysis shows a significant relationship between psychological empowerment and the work performance of elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District in Davao Oriental. Regression analysis verifies that psychological empowerment in terms of meaning, competence, autonomy, and influence were significant predictors of the work performance of elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental.

KEY WORDS

1. Psychological empowerment
2. work performance of teachers
3. educational management

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1. Introduction

Psychological empowerment is a concept originating from industrial-organizational psychology. Empowerment was defined as the opportunity an individual has for autonomy, choice, responsibility, and participation in decision-making in organizations. Similarly, psychological empowerment for teachers is a feeling that helps employees establish their work, complete meaningful work, and make im-

portant decisions. This psychological empowerment is important because everyone could get benefits in the form of increased loyalty, better decisions, improved quality, and a high level of work satisfaction for teachers. It was significant that teachers would thrive most when they have their basic psychological needs for autonomy, that was, experiencing a sense of volition psychological freedom, and competence.

Internationally, specifically in Arab, majority of the teachers suffer some problems because of some situations that immensely affect their work performance that includes the stress, anxiety, depression, and violence that negatively influence their teaching performance in the institution. These pressing problems become the major challenge among teachers that somehow make them more vulnerable and demotivated in some points in their teaching career (Lily et al., 2020). Further, it was revealed that in Spain, there was a report about the dilemmas experienced by the teachers in terms of workloads that teachers cannot focus their other functions because of their teaching loads that will consume their time that is supposed to be spent to other functions, and psychosomatic problems that really leads them to a risky situation, then, their performance is greatly affected which also affects the learning of the students (Gasco et al., 2020). Furthermore, Paresashvili (2021), revealed that improper distribution of functions and responsibilities is one of the reasons of conflict that may affect the work performance of the teachers because it makes them demotivated. In addition, it was proven in the result of the study that conflict in terms of management became a challenge that resulted to low productivity level and work performance is extremely affected. This is evident when the employees do not get the full support of their superiors and manifest less supervision. Additionally, in the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) implemented the Learning Continuity Plan to deliver education to learners. DepEd provided Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) with alternative learning delivery modalities for various types of learners, including modular, television-based, radio-based instruction, blended, and online. With this existing scenario, public school teachers have to modify to this incipient modification with increasing mandate of their workloads. In addition, teachers have to do other responsibilities aside from teaching, which may be the factor why teacher's teaching role is affected because it divides their time and it makes them demotivated. In Misamis Occidental, it was revealed in the study that only 3.98 percent of the teacher's work performance is manifested among teachers in the area of supervision and security and attributed to their job satisfaction in the organization. As a result, it was suggested that schools have to be provided with the faculty lounge so teachers can talk freely on their wellbeing. In addition, the Human Resource Department Officers have to strongly include in their teacher retention strategies the teachers' welfare packages. In the study, it aims to reduce the workloads of the teachers to effectively provide quality education and strengthen the power of supervision to guide the teachers to become well-rounded and effective (Baluyos et al., 2019). As such, recognizing the importance of work performance among public elementary teachers, the researcher has extensively reviewed the literature for possible variables that may affect it. Moreover, one variable emerged that could contribute to work performance, namely psychological empowerment (Royers, 2009). Additionally, it is manifested in the literature that the study group has a population gap that focused on employees (Inayat, 2021) and industrial workers (Gazi, 2022), however, less has been done on teachers especially the public elementary teachers who are leaders in building the foundation of the learners. Likewise, the methodology gap is also evident in the study, which focused on qualitative study like the research study of Mend and Sun (2019) about the impact of psychological empowerment on work performance among university faculty members in China. Also, a study of Mat and Rafida (2021), about the effects of psychological empowerment on employee performance, which employed qualitative design. Moreover, a study of Chunin (2019) titled psychological empowerment and morale on work performance predicting intention to stay

as teachers, which employed mixed methods design. Likewise, the researcher of this study has not encountered a study conducted in the Philippines especially in Davao Oriental on public elementary teachers using quantitative design. Moreover, this study's findings would help us understand the significant influence of psychological empowerment on the work performance of public elementary teachers. In addition, this

study may provide a huge opportunity to be included in the School Improvement Plan (SIP) in helping public elementary teachers achieve effective and efficient work performance. The researcher plans to disseminate the study result through the LAC session, PTA Meeting, District, Division, and Region Conference. Also, the researcher wants to present the study in the local, national, and international contexts.

2. Methodology

This chapter describes the research design, respondents, and procedure, which included the research instrument, data collection, statistical tools, and ethical considerations used in this study.

2.1. Research Design—The quantitative non-experimental research using causal effect was employed in this study. It was defined that this method determines the relationship among two or more variables and discovers their implications for cause and effect. Hence, this method was suited to describe the level of psychological empowerment and work performance of the elementary teachers engaged to it (Gabor, 2010). The independent variable was psychological empowerment. The dependent variable was the work performance. With this, statistical tools were utilized to determine the relationship among variables. This method was the best fit since the researcher of this undertaking wanted to find out the significant relationship and influence of psychological empowerment on the work performance among public elementary teachers in Banaybanay District under the Division of Davao Oriental.

2.2. Research Respondents—The respondents were the 158 public elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District under the Division of Davao Oriental who answered the survey questionnaires of the study. The district has a total population of 266 in the elementary schools. The researcher got a sample size of 158 from the total population using the Raosoft Calculator. The sample size of 158 was divided by eighteen

schools using purposive sampling. Therefore, 8 teachers from each school answered the survey questionnaire. Purposive sampling was used in selecting each school because the researcher had selected first the available subjects who met the criteria, in this case, the schools in Banaybanay District. In addition, purposive sampling was used in this study because each teacher in the school was chosen and had an equal right to be selected in the sample (Cresswell, 2003). Thus, the following criteria were set to achieve homogeneity: each respondent is a full-time public elementary school teacher who has rendered at least 5 years in service. Those who have rendered less than 5 years in their respective school and those who do not have teaching loads or non-teaching personnel were not included in the participation of this undertaking.

2.3. Research Instrument—The researcher of this study utilized two sets of questionnaires to gather the data from the respondents. The questionnaires were adapted and modified to complete the questions and to suit the environment where the study was to be conducted. The panel of experts validated these sets of questionnaires in terms of content. In addition, these survey questionnaires underwent pilot testing for reliability purposes. The researcher of this study used the first adapted questionnaire for

psychological empowerment by Royer (2009) with 0.887 Cronbach's Alpha reliability statistics of all indicators: meaning, competence, autonomy, and influence. The first indicator, meaning, has 3 questions; the second indicator, competence, has 3 questions; the third indicator, autonomy, has 3 questions; and the influence, as the last indicator, has 3 questions. The study's independent variable, psychological empowerment, was measured through its indicators. The scale below would be the basis of the study's quantification.

Range of Mean Descriptive Level Interpretation

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	The psychological empowerment is always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	The psychological empowerment is oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	The psychological empowerment is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	The psychological empowerment is rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	The psychological empowerment is never evident.

The researcher used the last questionnaire for the dependent variable, which was work performance. This questionnaire consists of three indicators: task performance with .79 Cronbach's alpha, contextual performance with .83 Cronbach's alpha, and counterproductive work behavior with .89 Cronbach's alpha reliability statistics value (Widyastuti, 2018). To determine the level of work performance, the mean scores were computed and analyzed using the following scale.

Range of Mean Descriptive Level Interpretation

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	The work performance is always observed.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	The work performance is oftentimes observed.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	The work performance is sometimes observed.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	The work performance is rarely observed.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	The work performance is never observed.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—After validating the research questionnaires, the researcher underwent the following steps in conducting the study. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured permission to conduct the study, with the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters endorsed to the principals of the selected public schools in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher distributed the research instrument to the respondents after they had been approved to conduct the study. In the distribution process, the researcher discussed how to answer the survey questionnaires and explained to the respondents the benefits of the study, which

would be the basis for improving their work performance. To administer the questionnaires, the researcher conducted a face-to-face interaction with the respondents. Furthermore, the study’s respondents were informed that they can withdraw their participation when they feel violated or discriminated during the administration of the questionnaire. Also, the researcher has provided a token intended for the teachers as a sign of his great appreciation for their participa-

tion of this study. The teachers were given time to answer the survey questionnaires, and after, the researcher retrieved the questionnaires, and the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After retrieving the survey questionnaires, each respondent’s scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After this, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was used to determine the level of psychological empowerment and work performance. Pearson

Product Moment Correlation. This was used to determine the significant relationship between psychological empowerment and work performance. Multiple Regression. This was used to determine the significant influence of psychological empowerment on work performance.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the objectives of the study as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extents of psychological empowerment and work performance of teachers; the significant relationship among the variables, the influence of psychological empowerment on the work performance of elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental.

Overall, the results in Table 1 summarize the extent of psychological empowerment of the public elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental. The overall mean score on psychological empowerment

is 4.30, described as very extensive and interpreted as always evident among public elementary teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Psychological Empowerment of Teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Meaning	4.53	Very Extensive
Competence	4.48	Very Extensive
Autonomy	4.23	Very Extensive
Influence	3.95	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.30	Very Extensive

With its indicators: Performance, which refers to the result of the efforts of every employee; autonomy, which allows individuals to limit their exposure to stressors and be able to choose their tasks; influence, which allows the employees to be engaged in the different decisions and plans of the school while giving trust and confidence. Meanwhile, the dependent variable of the study is the work performance, which consists of three indicators, namely: task performance, which refers to behaviors that contribute to the production of a good service or performance; contextual performance which contributes to the goals of the organization by contributing to its social and psychological environment; counterproductive work behavior, defined as voluntary behavior that harms the well-being of the organization. The result of the study supports the findings of the study of Erstad (2009), which revealed that empowerment is providing opportunities that will enable the employees like teachers to make decisions about the work they do especially with their teaching responsibilities and providing an organizational environment where the school leaders give full support and motivation to the teachers while they can take the responsibility of their individual activities and improve their quality of their work condition. In addition, it was revealed in the study that employees in the age range of 37-48 wanted most influence on decisions involving themselves and involving the organization, and those younger than 25 or older than 48 did not want as much influence as those aged between 25 and 48. This is contrast with Miller and Prichard (1992), who found that younger employees wanted more influence to be manifested in the organization.

The findings support the proposition of Periyasamy (2021), which revealed that employees are usually their own worst critics, asking employees about their performance can be effective;

Therefore, seasoned employees or teachers in the organization may give their full support and supervision to the young employees who need more influence from them and these seasoned teachers must be the role model in the school so that younger employees may look up to them. As employee empowerment activities require a structure where the administrators share authority and responsibility with the employees, it needs a different administrator profile other than its classical definition (Demirbilek Türkan, 2008). Additionally, it is hard to achieve success in employee empowerment if it becomes a target that is established by top executives for the organizational goals only and does not consider the expectations and desires of the employees who are supposed to be the main focus in the empowerment process (Koçel, 2003).

Overall, the results in Table 2 reflect the summary of the extent of the work performance of the public elementary teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental. The overall mean score of teachers' work performance is 3.75, which is described as very extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. As shown in the table, teachers' work performance in terms of task performance got the highest mean score of 4.47, described as very extensive and interpreted as always observed. The contextual performance has a mean score of 4.36, which is described as very extensive and interpreted as always observed. The counterproductive work behavior obtained the lowest mean score of 2.41, which was described as less extensive and interpreted as rarely observed among public elementary teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental.

lative; this helps them understand where they are lagging and helps them over time; their immediate supervisor – measure how well their subordinates understand their tasks, collaborates with

Table 2. Summary of the Work Performance of Elementary Teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Task Performance	4.47	Very Extensive
Contextual Performance	4.36	Very Extensive
Counterproductive Work Behavior	2.41	Less Extensive
Overall Mean	3.75	Extensive

other members, and show dedication to work; and peers – getting feedback from the group they work with is important to understand if their collaborative efforts are successful. Measuring employee performance can help in identifying possible faults in employee training programs and guide them on how to improve; these are how to measure work performance based on the sources according to Periyasamy (2021): the employees themselves - people are usually their own worst critics, asking an employee about their performance can be effective, this helped them understand where they are lagging and help them over time; their immediate supervisors measure how well their subordinates understand their tasks, collaborates with other members, and show dedication to work; and peers – getting feedback from the group they work with is important to understand if their collaborative efforts are successful. The result of the study is also supported by the proposition of Sulamin (2001), which reveals that in a general understanding among researchers, performance is an essential variable in work organization and has become a significant indicator in measuring organizational performance in many studies. Employee performance can also be measured by combining expected behavior and task-related aspects, even though financial figures often de-

termine performance. In reality, performance based on an absolute value or relative judgment may reflect overall organizational performance. However, it asserted that performance measure based on performance appraisal items offers higher reliability in evaluating performance.

Relationship Between Psychological Empowerment And Work Performance of Elementary Teachers In Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental

The results of the analysis of the relationship between psychological empowerment and work performance of public elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental, are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the mentioned variables. As reflected, Table 3 shows that psychological empowerment has a significant positive relationship with the work performance of the public elementary teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental, with a p-value of .000, which is lesser than the level of significance (two-tailed) ($r=0.705$, $p<0.05$). It implies that in every unit of psychological empowerment increased; there is a corresponding unit in the work performance of the elementary teachers increased.

Moreover, the table shows that psychological empowerment in terms of meaning, competence, autonomy, and influence are significantly correlated with the work performance of

the public elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental, as evidenced by the correlation coefficient values of 0.765, 0.645, 0.821 and 0.780. This leads to the rejec-

Table 3. Relationship Between Psychological Empowerment and Work Performance of Elementary Teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental

Psychological Empowerment	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Meaning	0.765*	.000	Significant	Reject H0
Competence	0.645*	.000	Significant	Reject H0
Autonomy	0.821*	.000	Significant	Reject H0
Influence	0.780*	.000	Significant	Reject H0
Overall	0.706*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0

*Significant @ p<0.05

tion of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between psychological empowerment and work performance of the public elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental. Further, the result is supported by the investigation conducted by Meng and Sun (2019), which revealed that psychological empowerment was positively correlated with work performance among employees. Furthermore, the result of the study showed that the positive role of psychological empowerment on work performance was realized mainly through two dimensions, meaning and competence. Also, it was suggested in the study that the schools should recognize the role of psychological empowerment and create a supportive environment to promote professional development that can increase the organization’s productivity.

Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R squared value of 0.428 indicates that psychological empowerment has contributed significantly to the variability of work performance of the public elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental, by 42.80 from the total variability. Therefore, the remaining 57.20 is attributed to other factors not included in the study. In addition, table 11 shows that there are domains of psychological empowerment that significantly influence the work performance of the public elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao

Domains of Psychological Empowerment that Significantly Influence the Work Performance of Elementary Teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental

The significance of the influence of psychological empowerment on the work performance of the public elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental, was analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis. Table 4 shows that psychological empowerment is considered a predictor of work performance of the public elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental; the model is significant, as evidenced by an F-value of 23.288 with p<0.05. Therefore, psychological empowerment predicts the work performance of the public elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental.

Oriental. This table indicates that psychological empowerment in terms of meaning, competence, autonomy, and influence are significant when considered as predictors of the work performance of public elementary teachers. This implies that the extent of psychological empowerment of the public elementary teachers increases by 0.291, 0.124, 0.135 and 0.332 for each unit increase in psychological empowerment of public elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental. Thus, this leads to the rejection of null hypothesis that none of the domain of the psychological

Table 4. Domains of Psychological Empowerment that Significantly Influence the Work Performance of Elementary Teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental

Psychological Empowerment	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value	Decisions
Meaning	.291*	.327	.078	.000	Reject H0
Competence	.124*	.134	.062	.000	Reject H0
Autonomy	.135	.124	.065	.000	Reject H0
Influence	.332*	.226	.063	.000	Reject H0

R² = 0.428
 F-value = 23.288**
 p-value = 0.000

*Significant @ p<0.05
 **Significant @ p<0.01

empowerment significantly influences the work performance of the public elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher’s conclusion and recommendation. The discussions were supported by the literature in the first chapters, and the conclusions were based on the statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary goal of this study was to assess which domains of transformational leadership significantly influence the motivation of elementary school teachers using a non-experimental quantitative design using a descriptive-predictive technique. The researcher selected 158 public elementary school teachers under Banaybanay District in Davao Oriental using the Raosoft calculator as respondents of this undertaking through a stratified random sampling method. In data collection, the researcher utilized adapted and modified survey questionnaires that underwent pilot testing to ensure the reliability and internal consistency of the items and were validated by expert validators. Based on the results, the summary of the findings was the following: The extent of psychological empowerment of teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental, has an overall mean score of 4.30, which was described as very extensive and interpreted as always manifested. psychological empowerment of teachers in terms of meaning, competence, autonomy, and Influence obtained mean scores of 4.53, 4.48, 4.48, and 3.95, respectively. The extent of elementary teachers’ work performance in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental, has an overall mean score of 3.75, described as extensive and interpreted as always observed. The motivation of elementary teachers in terms of task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior obtained a mean score of 4.47, 4.36, and 2.41, respectively. The study’s results showed that teachers’ psychological empowerment has a significant positive relationship with their work performance in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental, with a p-value of .000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This leads the researcher to reject the null hypothesis that there was no significant relationship between transformational leadership and the motivation of elementary school teachers in Ba-

banaybanay District, Davao Oriental. Overall, the psychological empowerment of teachers significantly influences the work performance of elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District in Davao Oriental, as evidenced by the F-value of 54.80 and $p < 0.05$. The r squared of 0.428 indicated that the psychological empowerment of teachers had contributed significantly to elementary school teachers' performance variability in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental, by 43.90 of the total variability. Furthermore, psychological empowerment of teachers in terms of meaning, competence, autonomy, and Influence were found to be significant predictors of motivation of elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District in Davao Oriental, as indicated by the regression coefficient values of 0.291, 0.124, 0.135 and 0.332, respectively.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of the study, several conclusions were generated:

The extent of psychological empowerment of teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental, in terms of psychological empowerment of teachers in terms of meaning, competence, autonomy, and Influence was described as very extensive and interpreted as always manifested. The extent of elementary teachers' work performance in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental, in terms of task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior, was extensive. The study's results showed that teachers' psychological empowerment has a significant positive relationship with their work performance in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental, with a p -value of .000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This leads the researcher to reject the null hypothesis, there was a significant relationship between teachers' psychological empowerment and the work performance of elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental. Overall, the psychological empowerment of teachers significantly influences the work performance of

elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District in Davao Oriental. The r squared indicated that the psychological empowerment of teachers contributed to the total variability of elementary school teachers' performance variability in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental. Furthermore, the psychological empowerment of teachers in terms of meaning, competence, autonomy, and Influence were found to be significant predictors of motivation of elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District in Davao Oriental.

4.3. Recommendations—It is recommended that the school heads of Banaybanay District in Davao Oriental continue to empower their transformational leadership by transforming the teachers to hone their skills and talents, especially in developing their teaching prowess to improve the school performance and achievement and the betterment of the learners. Further, it may be recommended that these school heads continue to display a sense of power and confidence while providing complete trust among teachers. Furthermore, transformational leadership could be manifested in the organization when the leaders continue to spend time teaching and coaching the teachers and helping them develop their strengths. On the one hand, it may be recommended that elementary school teachers sustain their motivation with their duties and responsibilities as catalysts of change to produce well-rounded individuals. As part of this, the Department of Education ensures that teachers receive benefits to increase their interest in teaching so they may feel secure and safe in the organization where their efforts and sacrifices are recognized and valued. Moreover, it may be recommended that good physical conditions be provided so that the teacher-employees in the organization feel secure in their jobs. Moreover, it was revealed that transformational leadership only contributes 54.80 of the total variability of motivation of elementary school teachers in Banaybanay District, Davao Oriental. Therefore,

the researcher may recommend that other researchers conduct a study using other variables that could be predictors of teacher motivation that could be conducted in a larger context.

5. References

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